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ASSESSMENT OF WATER SAMPLES FROM THE OXUD VILLAGE

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The results of the conducted research have shown that there are significant differences in the physico-chemical parameters of water samples collected from the Kish River and artesian wells in the Oxud village area of Sheki District. These differences can be attributed to various hydrogeological and ecological factors. The Kish River belongs to the category of surface waters and is formed as a result of atmospheric precipitation, surface runoff, and direct interaction with soil. For this reason, the river water often exhibits variability in parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen content, and other indicators. In contrast, artesian waters are extracted from natural aquifer layers located deep underground and have minimal contact with the atmosphere, resulting in a more stable physico-chemical composition. However, this stability does not imply complete protection from contamination. On the contrary, artesian water sources may be subjected to long-term and gradual pollution processes, primarily due to the leaching of nitrogen-containing fertilizers used in agriculture, which infiltrate through soil layers and reach the groundwater. It was determined that the water of the Kish River is characterized by high dissolved oxygen content and relatively low electrical conductivity and mineral composition. These indicators confirm that the river water is subject to dynamic natural aeration processes. On the other hand, the higher degree of mineralization in the artesian water, along with elevated concentrations of compounds such as ammonium and nitrate, indicates the influence of agricultural activities on the subsurface water cycle. Thus, the comparative analysis clearly demonstrates that factors affecting water quality are not only related to natural geological structure and climatic conditions but are also directly linked to human activity. Identifying these differences is of great importance for the safe use of drinking water and the sustainable monitoring of the environment.

Keywords: water quality, analysis, heavy metals, pollution, environmental monitoring.

Оценка проб воды из села Охуд

С.Р. Гаджиева, Э.М. Гадирова, С.В. Каримова

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Результаты проведённых исследований показали наличие существенных различий в физико-химических показателях проб воды, отобранных из реки Киш и артезианских скважин на территории села Охуд Шекинского района. Эти различия обусловлены различными гидрогеологическими и экологическими факторами. Река Киш относится к категории поверхностных вод и формируется за счёт атмосферных осадков, поверхностного стока и непосредственного взаимодействия с почвенным покровом. В связи с этим речная вода

характеризуется изменчивостью таких параметров, как температура, рН, содержание растворённого кислорода и другие показатели.

В отличие от неё, артезианские воды извлекаются из природных водоносных горизонтов, расположенных на значительной глубине, и имеют минимальный контакт с атмосферой, что обуславливает более стабильный физико-химический состав. Однако такая стабильность не означает полной защищённости от загрязнения. Напротив, артезианские источники могут подвергаться длительным и постепенным процессам загрязнения, главным образом вследствие вымывания азотсодержащих удобрений, используемых в сельском хозяйстве, которые проникают через почвенные слои и достигают грунтовых вод.

Установлено, что вода реки Киш характеризуется высоким содержанием растворённого кислорода и относительно низкими показателями электропроводности и минерализации, что свидетельствует о динамичных процессах естественной аэрации. В то же время более высокая степень минерализации артезианской воды, а также повышенные концентрации аммония и нитратов указывают на влияние сельскохозяйственной деятельности на подземный водный цикл. Таким образом, сравнительный анализ наглядно демонстрирует, что факторы, влияющие на качество воды, связаны не только с природным геологическим строением и климатическими условиями, но и напрямую обусловлены антропогенной деятельностью. Выявление данных различий имеет важное значение для безопасного использования питьевой воды и устойчивого экологического мониторинга.

Ключевые слова: качество воды, анализ, тяжёлые металлы, загрязнение, экологический мониторинг.

Охуд кишлоғидаги сув намуналарини баҳолаш
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Олиб борилган тадқиқотлар натижалари Шеки тумани Охуд кишлоғи худудидаги Киш дарёси ва артезиан кудуқларидан олинган сув намуналарининг физик-кимёвий кўрсаткичларида сезиларли фарқлар мавжудлигини кўрсатди. Ушбу фарқлар турли гидрогеологик ва экологик омиллар билан изоҳланади. Киш дарёси юза сувлари тоифасига кириб, атмосфера ёғинлари, ер усти оқими ҳамда тупроқ билан бевосита ўзаро таъсир натижасида шаклланади. Шу сабабли, дарё сувида ҳарорат, рН кўрсаткичи, эриган кислород миқдори ва бошқа параметрларнинг ўзгарувчанлиги кузатилади.

Бундан фарқли равишда, артезиан сувлари ер қаърида жойлашган табиий сув қатламларидан олинадиган ва атмосфера билан алоқаси жуда кам бўлгани сабабли, уларнинг физик-кимёвий таркиби нисбатан барқарор ҳисобланади. Бироқ, бу барқарорлик уларнинг ифлосланишдан тўлиқ ҳимояланганини аниқламайди. Аксинча, артезиан сув манбалари кишлоқ хўжалигида қўлланиладиган азотли ўғитларнинг тупроқ орқали ювилиб, ер ости сувларига

сингиб бориши натижасида узоқ муддатли ва секин ифлосланиш жараёнларига дучор бўлиши мумкин.

Тадқиқотлар натижасида Киш дарёси суви эриган кислород миқдорининг юқорилиги ҳамда электропроводлик ва минерал таркибнинг нисбатан пастлиги билан ажралиб туриши аниқланди. Бу кўрсаткичлар дарё сувида табиий аэрация жараёнлари фаол кечаётганини тасдиқлайди. Шу билан бирга, артезиан сувларида минераллашув даражасининг юқорилиги, аммоний ва нитрат каби бирикмалар концентрациясининг ошганлиги қишлоқ хўжалиги фаолиятининг ер ости сув айланмасига таъсирини кўрсатади. Шу тариқа, қиёсий таҳлил сув сифатига таъсир этувчи омиллар нафақат табиий геологик тузилиш ва иқлим шароитлари, балки инсон фаолияти билан ҳам бевосита боғлиқ эканлигини яққол намоён этади. Мазкур фарқларни аниқлаш ичимлик сувидан хавфсиз фойдаланиш ва атроф-муҳитни барқарор мониторинг қилиш учун муҳим аҳамиятга эга.

Калит сўзлар: сув сифати, таҳлил, оғир металлар, ифлосланиш, экологик мониторинг.

Introduction

Water resources are an indispensable asset for life and play a vital role in maintaining ecosystems and public health. The quality of water resources is influenced by both natural and anthropogenic factors, and these impacts can lead to changes in the physico-chemical composition of water. Agricultural activities, the use of fertilizers and pesticides, soil erosion, and industrial discharges are among the primary contributors to such changes [1]. The aim of this study is to analyze the ecochemical characteristics of water samples collected from the Oxud village area in the Sheki district and to evaluate potential ecological risks by comparing the results with international standards. Global studies on water quality indicators show that parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen, electrical conductivity, major ions (NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}), and heavy metals (Fe, Cu, Cd, As) are among the most significant indicators [2,3]. According to the 2022 reports by WHO and UNEP, approximately 30% of drinking water sources have become chemically and biologically unsafe due to human activities. In particular, the increase in the levels of nitrate and ammonium compounds occurs as a result of leaching from soils, predominantly in agricultural regions. The presence of heavy metals in water sources also poses a serious threat. Even at low concentrations, elements such as arsenic, cadmium, and copper can cause chronic effects [4].

Experimental Part

The research was conducted in Oxud village, located in the Sheki district of northwestern Azerbaijan, on the southern slopes of the Greater Caucasus Mountains. The terrain of the village mainly consists of foothill zones, which influence the area's hydrometeorological and hydrogeological conditions. The climate is moderately warm and semi-arid, with an average annual temperature of 10–12°C and an annual precipitation of 600–800 mm. The area is predominantly inhabited by a population engaged in agricultural activities. Various nitrogen- and phosphorus-based mineral

fertilizers are used in crop fields, which may affect both surface and groundwater quality. The main water sources in Oxud village are the flow of the local *Kish* River and artesian wells located at various depths. The Kish River, as a surface water body with open flow, is more exposed to surface pollution. In contrast, artesian waters originate from deeper geological layers and typically exhibit more stable physico-chemical properties. A comparative analysis of these distinct water sources is essential for evaluating water quality and ecological conditions.

Results and Discussion

Water samples were collected during the spring season, specifically in April and May of 2025. The samples were collected in the morning, following standard laboratory procedures, and stored in sterile plastic bottles. Approximately 2 liters of water were taken from each sampling point and immediately transported to the laboratory for analysis. The samples were collected from the middle flow section of the Kish River and the main artesian well used for drinking water in the village. During sample collection, the water temperature and pH levels were measured on-site using portable devices. The collected water samples were analyzed at the “Khazar Ecological Laboratory” in Baku, equipped with modern analytical equipment. Standard procedures were applied for both physico-chemical and chemical parameter analyses.

Physical Parameter Analysis Methods.

Temperature: Measured using an electronic thermometer.

pH: Measured on-site using a portable pH meter.

Electrical Conductivity (EC): Determined using a conductivity meter, with results expressed in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

Table 1. Analysis of physical parameters of water samples

Indicators	Kish River	Artesian water
pH	6.8	7.6
Temperature 23°C	23.27	23.17
Oxygen content (mg/l)	11.2	1.1
Electrical conductivity($\mu\text{S}/\text{sm}$)	160-300	650-1400
Density (g/sm^3)	1.003	1.09

Density: Determined by the pycnometric method.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO): Measured using the Winkler method or a DO meter.

Chemical Parameter Analysis Methods.

Ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-) ions: The concentration was determined using colorimetric or ion chromatography methods.

Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) ions: Determined using the BaCl_2 precipitation method.

Heavy metals – copper (Cu^{2+}), iron ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$), cadmium (Cd^{2+}), and arsenic (As^{3+}):

Measured using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) method [5]. During the analysis, the water safety parameters were compared with the guidelines of the World Health Organization (WHO), the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and the normative documents of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The analysis of the physical and chemical parameters of the water samples provides significant information regarding the ecological and sanitary status of the Water. The results show that there are some important differences between the Kish River water and the artesian water. In the case of the Kish River, the pH value was recorded as 6.8, while the artesian water had a pH of 7.6. These values (Table 1) indicate the degree of neutrality of the water. The recommended pH range for drinking water is between 6.5 and 8.5 [6-8]. While both water sources fall within this range, the lower pH in the Kish River suggests that it is slightly more acidic. This could be due to precipitation and interaction with soil.

Temperature: In both samples, the temperature is around 23°C. Water temperature directly affects biochemical reactions and the amount of dissolved oxygen. The relatively stable temperature indicates that the water sources are in accordance with the climatic and flow conditions.

Dissolved Oxygen: The oxygen level in the Kish River was 11.2 mg/l, which is considered high. In contrast, the oxygen level in the artesian water was only 1.1 mg/l. High oxygen levels in flowing waters occur due to natural aeration, while in stationary, deep, and enclosed environments, oxygen levels tend to decrease. This difference suggests that artesian water may be less suitable for living organisms and could provide conditions for the growth of anaerobic microorganisms .

Electrical Conductivity: The electrical conductivity in the Kish River ranged from 160 to 300 µS/cm, while in the artesian water, it ranged from 650 to 1400 µS/cm. The higher electrical conductivity indicates a higher level of mineralization in the water. The greater mineral content in artesian waters can be explained by the dissolution of salts from natural geological layers. This also affects the hardness of the water, which could pose problems for domestic use.

Density: The density of the Kish River water was 1.003 g/cm³, while the artesian water had a density of 1.09 g/cm³. This difference indicates that the artesian water contains more dissolved substances (salts, minerals).

Table 2. Anion analysis of water samples

Indicators	Kish river	Artesian water
Ammonium, NH ₄ mq/l	<0.04	0.17
Nitrates,(NO ₃ ⁻) mq/l	3.3	47
Sulfates, (SO ₄ ²⁻) mq/l	15	28

Ammonium (NH₄⁺): The ammonium concentration in the Kish River was <0.04 mg/l, while in the artesian water, it was 0.17 mg/l. The high concentration of ammonium is linked to agricultural activities and the infiltration of organic waste into groundwater. According to WHO, the recommended maximum limit for ammonium in

drinking water is 0.5 mg/l. Although artesian water does not exceed this limit, it still requires careful monitoring.

Nitrate (NO_3^-): The concentration of nitrate in the Kish River was 3.3 mg/l, while in the artesian water, it was 47 mg/l. The maximum permissible limit for nitrate, according to WHO, is 50 mg/l. Since the artesian water is close to this threshold, it is considered a potential source of danger. High nitrate levels, especially in infants, increase the risk of “methemoglobinemia” (blue baby syndrome).

Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}): The levels of sulfate were measured at 15 mg/l and 28 mg/l, respectively. These values are much lower than the WHO limit of 250 mg/l, and both water sources are considered safe in this regard. Sulfates are primarily of geological origin and can affect the taste of the water.

Table 3. Cation analysis of water samples

Indicators	Kish river	Artesian water
Mis (Cu) mq/l	<0.008	<0.008
Iron (Fe) mq/l	<0.01	<0.01
Cadmium(Cd)mq/l	<0.0015	<0.0015
Arsenic(As)mq/l	<0.01	<0.01

Heavy Metals (Cu, Fe, Cd, As): The concentrations of all these metals were below the detectable minimum limit. This indicates that the risk of heavy metal contamination in the studied areas is low. The minimal presence of cadmium and arsenic is a positive indicator from an ecotoxicological perspective [9-12].

Conclusion

In terms of physical parameters, the Kish River water has relatively higher oxygen levels (11.2 mg/l), with a pH value of 6.8, indicating a slightly acidic environment (Table 1). In contrast, the artesian water has significantly lower oxygen levels (1.1 mg/l), which is explained by its underground origin and lack of contact with air. This situation aligns with international studies confirming the oxygen scarcity in groundwater. Chemical parameters reveal more traces of anthropogenic impacts (Table 2 and Table 3). The nitrate (47mg/l) and ammonium (0.17mg/l) values in artesian water are significantly higher compared to the Kish River ($\text{NO}_3 = 3.3 \text{ mg/l}$; $\text{NH}_4 = <0.04 \text{ mg/l}$). This indicates the possibility of agricultural fertilizers and substances leaching from the soil and entering underground waters .

In general, both water sources are below the recommended limits for heavy metals (Cu, Fe, Cd, As) according to WHO and EPA, indicating relatively clean water in this regard. However, the elevated levels of nitrate and ammonium, especially in the artesian source, may pose long-term health risks. The Kish River water is more oxygenated and has balanced physical parameters. Artesian water shows a higher risk of contamination due to elevated concentrations of nitrate and ammonium. Both sources are within safety limits for heavy metals. The high electrical conductivity in artesian water indicates a higher degree of mineralization.

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